

SQUEEZE FLOW TESTING OF POLYPROPYLENE AND GLASS MAT THERMOPLASTICS AT COMPRESSION MOULDING STRAIN RATES

J. H. Bland¹, H. E. N. Bersee² and A. G. Gibson³

^{1,3} *Centre for Composite Materials Engineering, Materials Division, Dept. of Mechanical, Materials and Manufacturing Engineering, Herschel Building, University of Newcastle, Newcastle upon Tyne, U.K.*

² *Shell Research and Technology Centre, Amsterdam, Badhuisweg 3, 1031 CM Amsterdam, The Netherlands.*

SUMMARY: Axisymmetric biaxial squeeze flow tests have been carried out on continuous fibre Glass Mat Thermoplastic (GMT) and also on samples of the unfilled polypropylene matrix. Tests were carried out at constant squeezing rates representative of conditions in the compression moulding process. Lubricated squeeze flow was also used to study biaxial extensional flow. The results of lubricated and unlubricated tests on similar samples are compared and the flow characteristics identified. Unlubricated squeeze flow of GMT can be characterised by three regions: 1) a short 'start-up' period of elastic material compression, 2) predominantly extensional flow over the majority of the squeezing range and 3) shear-dominated flow at small plate separations. Results from lubricated and unlubricated tests on GMT under the same conditions are very similar for the first half of the total deformation, with the squeezing force in the unlubricated condition rising rapidly after further flow as shear flow effects become more significant.

KEYWORDS: Glass Mat Thermoplastic, GMT, polypropylene, rheology, lubricated squeeze flow, biaxial extensional flow

INTRODUCTION

The compression moulding of Glass Mat Thermoplastics (GMTs) has become a popular route for the high-volume production of complex semi-structural parts, especially for the automotive industry. There is, however, a relative lack of knowledge of the flow behaviour of GMT during moulding, which prevents a full understanding of the process and hinders the development of mould-filling predictions. The squeeze flow technique, shown schematically in Fig. 1, has received much interest as a study technique for compression moulding materials since the biaxial flow field generated is broadly representative of the flow mechanism found in the moulding process. In this technique, a disc-shaped sample of molten material is squeezed between heated parallel plates which move together under a controlled approach. The material response in terms of the squeezing force and plate separation is measured throughout the test.

Figure 1: Schematic diagram of constant volume squeeze flow

In this work, a constant velocity squeezing condition is imposed with the fastest squeezing rates used representative of those found in the moulding process. Samples of the unfilled polypropylene matrix material with a similar geometry to the GMT samples used were tested to examine the effect of the mat reinforcement on flow behaviour.

The squeeze flow technique may be operated under lubricated or unlubricated conditions. Unlubricated squeeze flow of polymer melts creates a shear flow field in the test material and the technique can be used to measure shear viscosity [1,2] under certain conditions. The effect of lubrication is to change the gapwise velocity profile from a near-parabolic shape (Fig. 2(a)) to that of a ‘plug flow’ (biaxial extension) with complete material slippage at the plate surfaces, as shown in Fig. 2(b). There should, then, be a significantly different material response between the two conditions for tests on unfilled materials.

Figure 2: Velocity profiles in squeeze flow

However, previous work [3,4] on the *unlubricated* squeeze flow of GMT has demonstrated the predominance of extensional flow during squeezing. It was suggested, however, that the flow mechanism involved a thin shearing layer of polypropylene matrix acting as a lubricant at the plate surface while the bulk material underwent biaxial extension as shown in Fig. 2(c). Also, it is probable that the flow field was shear-dominated at small plate separations.

Lubricated squeeze flow, in which the flow mechanism is pure biaxial extension, should be a useful comparison with which to test these conclusions.

THEORY

The constant volume squeeze flow technique is shown schematically in Fig. 1. A molten disc-shaped sample is squeezed between two parallel heated plates under a constant squeezing rate. The sample thickness decreases as the plates approach one another and the sample radius increases as the material flows. Power law constitutive equations are used to model the flow behaviour and the squeezing force is strongly dependent on the flow boundary conditions at the plate surfaces.

Unlubricated Squeeze Flow

Under unlubricated conditions, a ‘no-slip’ condition is imposed at the surfaces of the plates. For unfilled polymer melts, this results in a pure shear flow field with a near-parabolic gapwise velocity profile. The power law constitutive equation for shear flow gives the shear stress as

$$\tau = A_s \dot{\gamma}^m \quad (1)$$

where A_s is the shear flow power law constant, m the power law index and $\dot{\gamma}$ the shear rate. The Scott equation [5] describes the variation of squeezing force with plate separation for a power law fluid;

$$F_{ca} = \left(\frac{2m+1}{m} \right)^m \left(\frac{2\pi A_s R^{m+3}}{m+3} \right) \left(\frac{u^m}{h^{2m+1}} \right) \quad (2)$$

where u is the squeezing velocity, h the instantaneous plate separation and R the sample radius. This equation is derived for constant area tests (sample diameter equal to plate diameter) and may be modified for application to constant volume tests to give

$$F_{cv} = \left(\frac{2m+1}{m} \right)^m \left(\frac{2VA_s R_o^{m+1}}{m+3} \right) (h_o)^{\frac{m+1}{2}} \left(\frac{u^m}{h^{\frac{5m+5}{2}}} \right) \quad (3)$$

where V is the sample volume and R_o and h_o the initial sample radius and thickness respectively.

Lubricated Squeeze Flow

The ‘no-slip’ condition is eliminated if a layer of lubricant is applied to the surface of the plates and to the sample, which has the effect of causing complete wall slip and eliminating the shear component of flow. In the absence of a shear contribution to the flow field, the material flows in biaxial extension with the radial velocity proportional to the radial position, r , but constant with respect to vertical position, z , between the plates (Fig. 2(b)).

From the power law constitutive equation, the strain rate-dependent extending stress is given by

$$\sigma = A_e \dot{\epsilon}^n \quad (4)$$

where A_e is the extensional flow power law parameter and n is the power law index. For the squeeze flow geometry, $\dot{\epsilon}$, the strain rate, is given by

$$\dot{\epsilon} = \left(\frac{u}{h} \right) \quad (5)$$

where u is the squeezing rate and h the instantaneous plate separation. An expression for the squeezing force during the test may be obtained directly from Eqn (4) and, using the constant volume assumption to describe the increasing sample radius, yields

$$F_{cv} = \left(\frac{V}{h} \right) A_e \left(\frac{u}{h} \right)^n \quad (6)$$

In order to determine power law parameters, we rearrange this expression and, taking logarithms, obtain

$$\log(Fh) = \log(VA_e) + n \cdot \log(\dot{\epsilon}) \quad (7)$$

A double logarithmic plot of (Fh) vs. $(\dot{\epsilon})$ should therefore give a straight line of slope n with A_e being calculated from the intercept of the line with the vertical axis corresponding to unity strain rate. It should be noted that A_e is often found to be strain-dependent [6], as in the case of a strain-hardening material.

MATERIALS

Both polypropylene (Shell grade XS-6500-S) and GMT samples were made with the same nominal geometry. Pure polymer samples were made by melt pressing 85 g of polymer granules in a simple plate mould and yielded samples with an average diameter of 148 mm and a 4.5 mm thickness.

The GMT material used in this work was based on the continuous swirled fibre mat produced by Symalit of Switzerland. Commercial grades of GMT, however, contain some ground recycled material between mat layers and have a comparatively large variation in glass content over a given area (around $\pm 4\%$ by weight variation). In order to be able to determine volume fraction more accurately, maintain consistent sample quality and to vary glass content in future studies, samples were manufactured by compression moulding. The manufacture of samples 'in-house' also reduces the effects of data scatter due to the variation in commercial material specification from batch to batch. A simple 150 mm diameter closed circular mould was used and samples manufactured by film stacking and hot pressing. The polypropylene matrix is the same as that used in the pure polymer samples. Samples were inspected individually after moulding to ensure good quality test specimens. The final average dimensions of the samples were 149.9 mm diameter with a 3.9 mm thickness and an average glass content of 30% by weight.

SQUEEZE FLOW EQUIPMENT AND TEST PROCEDURES

Fig. 3 shows the equipment used. The 395 mm x 395 mm squeeze flow plates are supported by four sliding columns to provide lateral stability and the whole apparatus is mounted in a 500 kN servohydraulic testing frame. Electrical heating elements and water cooling channels are incorporated beneath each plate.

Figure 3: Photograph of Squeeze Flow Plates

Before testing, the plates are heated up with a separation of a few millimetres to allow for thermal expansion. Once the temperature had stabilised, the test programme opened the plates and the sample was placed in the centre of the lower plate. The plates are then closed to a separation of 5 mm and left for 10 minutes to allow the sample temperature to stabilise at 190°C. At the start of heating, the upper plate is not in contact with the GMT sample. This condition is imposed to allow for data correction due to the effects of internal friction and machine inertia at the start of machine movement. During heating, however, the GMT ‘lofts’ and contacts the upper plate. The initial movement of the plates reconsolidates the material and only squeezing in the final 3.9 mm is regarded as valid data. Once the sample is uniformly heated, the plates are driven together at the required velocity to a plate separation of 1 mm. The squeezing velocities used were 0.3, 1, 5, 10 and 20 mm/s. The same procedure is used for testing polypropylene samples, although lofting does not, of course, occur.

The most critical experimental factor in the lubricated squeeze flow technique is obtaining complete material slip at the plate surfaces. Silicon oils of various viscosities were used and the most effective lubricant determined by trial and error. The *quantity* of lubricant used was also found to be critical: too much and/or too high a viscosity of oil created an uneven lubricant layer and caused flow instabilities. A distorted sample shape resulted. With too little or too low a viscosity, incomplete wall slip occurred and pure extensional flow could not be achieved. In this work, tracers on the surfaces of the samples were used to assess the extent of slippage. Tracers were made from 5 mm lengths of thin carbon fibre/PEEK composite tape and were placed in shallow grooves in the sample surface as shown in Fig. 4. The position of the tracers after testing gives an indication of whether complete wall slip has been achieved. If complete wall slip is achieved, the tracers should remain at the outermost radial position on the sample. It was found that GMT was less sensitive to the lubrication method than was the

unfilled polypropylene, presumably due to the higher viscosity of the material. In all the tests, oil with a viscosity of 0.5 Pa.s was wiped on to the plates with a clean cloth prior to plate heating, with care being taken to apply as even a coating as possible. The surfaces of the test sample were also coated. After the test, when cooling was completed, the plates were degreased with acetone to ensure no residual oil build-up in subsequent tests.

Figure 4: Positioning of Tracers on Sample Surface to Assess Extent of Wall Slip

RESULTS

Polypropylene

Fig. 5 shows squeezing force vs. plate displacement plots for squeeze flow tests on polypropylene. Lubricated and non-lubricated tests are shown on the same plot for squeezing rates of 1, 10 and 20 mm/s. It can be seen that lubrication lowers the required squeezing force by around 50% for the whole range of squeezing.

Figure 5: Squeezing Force vs. Plate Displacement for Polypropylene Tests

Other workers have used the unlubricated and lubricated squeeze flow techniques to generate shear and extensional viscosity data for polymer melts [1,7]. It should be noted, however, that a state of approximately steady flow must be achieved for this purpose. With the squeezing rates used in this work, which are chosen to be representative of the compression moulding process, it is not possible to achieve a steady state (or a 'quasi-steady state', as is most often assumed) and the calculation of viscosity data would not be valid.

Glass Mat Thermoplastic

Experimental data from lubricated and unlubricated tests on GMT at three different squeezing rates are compared in Fig. 6. Again, lubrication lowers the squeezing force, but to a much lesser extent than in tests on pure polypropylene.

Figure 6: Squeezing Force vs. Plate Displacement for GMT

Squeezing force is similar for unlubricated and lubricated cases for about the first half of the test, with the force in the lubricated tests only slightly less than that for the unlubricated tests. At plate separations of less than about 2 mm, however, the force in the unlubricated tests increases much more sharply than that in the lubricated tests and the difference between the two becomes much larger.

A double logarithmic plot of (Fxh) vs. $\dot{\epsilon}$ may be constructed (see Eqn 7) for the lubricated test data as shown in Fig. 7. Here, a linear relation exists for each value of plate separation plotted. These lines have slope n and their intercept with the vertical axis shown can be used to calculate A_e .

There is a small variation of A_e with increasing strain, as shown in Fig. 8. In fact, a slight decrease in A_e occurs as plate separation decreases and the variation may be approximated with a polynomial relationship. The resulting equation may be substituted into Eqn 5 to describe the squeezing force in power law terms. A typical test is compared with this model in Fig. 9. It should be noted that the 'start-up' flow region, corresponding to elastic compression of the sample, at the beginning of the test is not described by this model.

Figure 7: Log. (Squeezing Force x Plate Separation) vs. Log. Strain Rate for Lubricated GMT Tests

Figure 8: Variation of Extensional Flow Power Law Parameter with Strain Rate for Lubricated Tests on GMT

Figure 9: Comparison of Extensional Flow Model with Experimental Results

DISCUSSION

The unlubricated squeeze flow tests on GMT in previous work [3] showed that the flow could be modelled as biaxial extension over a portion of the total range of plate separation. This region occurred after the initial elastic compression and before the flow became shear-dominated at small plate separations. In this region, the squeezing forces found in *lubricated* squeeze flow are very similar to, although slightly lower than, those with unlubricated conditions. It was also suggested that a thin polypropylene layer, acting as a lubricant, may exist at the plate surfaces in unlubricated squeeze flow, and the small discrepancy between unlubricated and lubricated results may be due to the force required to shear this thin polymer layer. This behaviour supports the evidence for the biaxial extension of GMT in unlubricated squeeze flow.

At small plate separations, the squeezing force in unlubricated tests rises much more rapidly than that in lubricated tests. This is to be expected if the flow field in unlubricated tests becomes increasingly dominated by shear at small plate separations. Lubricated GMT, conversely, continues to undergo extensional flow throughout the test, as indicated by the final position of the surface tracers.

As may be expected, the flow behaviour of the polypropylene matrix material is different. The absence of the glass mat reinforcement reduces squeezing forces by around 25% at the highest loads in unlubricated tests. The forces in these tests are significantly higher than those under lubricated conditions throughout the range of plate displacement. This discrepancy in force represents the two extremes of material flow: shear flow under unlubricated conditions, with biaxial extension occurring in lubricated tests.

CONCLUSIONS

The unlubricated squeeze flow of unfilled polypropylene is shear-dominated. This behaviour has been modelled using power law shear flow constitutive equations [1,2] and also used to generate shear viscosity data under condition of steady flow. The effect of lubricating the plate surfaces during testing is to lower the required squeeze force throughout the test as the material undergoes biaxial extension with a negligible shear flow contribution.

Flow of GMT in squeeze flow appears to consist of three regions: 1) a 'start-up' flow of elastic material compression, 2) biaxial extension over the majority of the squeezing range and 3) a shear-dominated flow at small plate separations. This is confirmed by results from lubricated squeeze flow tests. For the range of squeezing attributed to extension in unlubricated squeeze flow, the forces are similar to those seen in lubricated squeeze flow. In the shear-dominated region at small plate separations under unlubricated conditions, the forces are much higher than in lubricated flow.

This work has attempted to simulate conditions in the compression moulding process if conditions were isothermal. Flow of GMT under these conditions is predominately extensional and can be described to a good approximation by simple power law relations. During flow in thin sections, however, flow behaviour changes and shear flow becomes increasingly important, causing a sharp rise in squeezing force. A purely extensional model may underestimate actual pressing forces under these conditions and an accurate model of compression moulding must cater for these changes in flow conditions.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Mr. J. H. Bland would like to thank Shell Research and Technology Centre, Amsterdam for partial funding in this work under the Co-operative Award in Science and Engineering scheme. In addition, many useful discussions with Professor S. Toll of Chalmers University, Gothenburg, Sweden are gratefully acknowledged. Further funding from the Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council was also gratefully received.

REFERENCES

1. Laun, H. M. "Rheometry Towards Complex Flows: Squeeze Flow Technique" *Makromol. Chem., Macromol. Symp.*, Vol.56, 1992, pp.55-66.
2. Winther, G., Almdal, K. and Kramer, O., "Determination of Polymer Melt Viscosity by Squeezing Flow with Constant Plate Velocity", *Jnl. of Non-Newtonian Fluid Mech.*, Vol.39, 1991, pp.118-136
3. Kotiskos, G., Bland, J. H. and Gibson, A. G., "Squeeze Flow Testing of Glass Mat Thermoplastic Materials" *Composites A*, Vol.27A, No.12, 1996, pp.1195-1200.
4. Bland, J. H., Bersee, H. E. N. and Gibson, A. G., "Squeeze Flow of Polypropylene and Glass Mat Thermoplastics at Compression Moulding Strain Rates. Part II: Squeeze Flow of Glass Mat Thermoplastics" *Submitted to Composites A*.

5. Bird, R. B., Armstrong, R. C. and Hassager, O., *Dynamics of Polymeric Liquids; Volume 1*, 2nd Edition, J. Wiley & Sons, New York, 1987.
6. Collyer, A. A. and Clegg, D. W. (Eds.), *Rheological Measurement*, Elsevier Applied Science, London, 1988.
7. Hoover, K. C. & Tock, R. W., "Experimental Studies on the Biaxial Extensional Viscosity of Polypropylene" *Poly. Eng. & Sci.*, Vol.16, No.2, Feb.1976, pp.82-86.
8. Hsu, T. C. & Harrison, I. R., "Measurement of the Equibiaxial Elongational Viscosity of Polystyrene Using Lubricated Squeezing" *Poly. Eng. & Sci.*, Vol.31, No.4, Feb.1991, pp.223-230.